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mRNA Covid - 19 vaccination and myocarditis: no causal relationship

Research article

Ilija Barukčić¹

¹ Internist, Horandstrasse, 26441 Jever, Germany

* **Correspondence:** E-Mail: Barukcic@t-online.de;
Tel: +49-4466-333; Fax: +49-4466-333.

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Ilija Barukčić

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🌐 Website: WWW.CAUSATION.EU

✉ E-Mail: editor@causation.eu

☎ Phone: +(49) 4466 - 333

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Abstract**Background:**

How can we arrive at long-lasting knowledge with an appropriate degree of reliability. In this regard, it can prove helpful to rely on knowledge that has already been secured.

Methods:

A narrative style has been used.

Results:

The data of the study of Schwab et al. have been re-analysed.

Conclusion:

No causal relationship between mRNA Covid-19 vaccination and fatal myocarditis.

Keywords:

Messenger RNA-based Covid-19 Vaccination; Myocarditis; Cause; Effect; Causal relationship k; Causality; Causation

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☉ Reviewer 2: None.

☉ Reviewer 3: None.

1. Introduction

The clinical presentations of myocarditis¹ with symptoms like dyspnea, chest pain and arrhythmias such as atrial fibrillation, ventricular tachycardia, or heart block is very heterogeneous. This is one of the reasons why a simple and reliable diagnosis of myocarditis beyond any reasonable doubt is not always as easy as necessary. Very often, myocarditis is clinically latent and mild with resolution of symptoms without any medical treatment. However, in rare instances individuals required intensive care support² or even died. Unfortunately, in medical practice, the endomyocardial biopsy (EMB) as a diagnostic gold standard³ of myocarditis is used infrequently^{4, 5}. We cannot help but notice that even exact determination of the actual incidence of myocarditis is also difficult. Considering the overall circumstances, myocarditis is still a challenging diagnosis. Despite all the difficulties, we have a certain degree of evidence provided i.e. by studies which addressed the issue of sudden cardiac death in young people. Nonetheless, the reports of prevalence of myocarditis cases of sudden cardiac death in young people is ranging from 2 to 42%.^{6, 7, 8} Unfortunately, children and adults can also succumb to sudden cardiac death. In point of fact, a biopsy-proven myocarditis has been found in 9–16% of adult patients with unexplained non-ischæmic dilated cardiomyopathy (DCM)^{9, 10}. Biopsy-proven myocarditis has been reported in about 46% of sudden cardiac death of children with an identified cause of DCM¹¹. We have again and again to deal with difficulties, as in real life. Are

¹Hufnagel G, Pankuweit S, Richter A, Schönian U, Maisch B. The European Study of Epidemiology and Treatment of Cardiac Inflammatory Diseases (ESETCID). First epidemiological results. *Herz*. 2000 May;25(3):279-85. doi: 10.1007/s000590050021. PMID: 10904853.

²Kociol RD, Cooper LT, Fang JC, Moslehi JJ, Pang PS, Sabe MA, Shah RV, Sims DB, Thiene G, Vardeny O; American Heart Association Heart Failure and Transplantation Committee of the Council on Clinical Cardiology. Recognition and Initial Management of Fulminant Myocarditis: A Scientific Statement From the American Heart Association. *Circulation*. 2020 Feb 11;141(6):e69-e92. doi: 10.1161/CIR.0000000000000745. Epub 2020 Jan 6. PMID: 31902242.

³Richardson P, McKenna W, Bristow M, Maisch B, Mautner B, O'Connell J, Olsen E, Thiene G, Goodwin J, Gyarfás I, Martin I, Nordet P. Report of the 1995 World Health Organization/International Society and Federation of Cardiology Task Force on the Definition and Classification of cardiomyopathies. *Circulation*. 1996 Mar 1;93(5):841-2. doi: 10.1161/01.cir.93.5.841. PMID: 8598070.

⁴Leone O, Veinot JP, Angelini A, Baandrup UT, Basso C, Berry G, Bruneval P, Burke M, Butany J, Calabrese F, d'Amati G, Edwards WD, Fallon JT, Fishbein MC, Gallagher PJ, Halushka MK, McManus B, Pucci A, Rodriguez ER, Saffitz JE, Sheppard MN, Steenbergen C, Stone JR, Tan C, Thiene G, van der Wal AC, Winters GL. 2011 consensus statement on endomyocardial biopsy from the Association for European Cardiovascular Pathology and the Society for Cardiovascular Pathology. *Cardiovasc Pathol*. 2012 Jul-Aug;21(4):245-74. doi: 10.1016/j.carpath.2011.10.001. Epub 2011 Dec 3. PMID: 22137237.

⁵Kindermann I, Barth C, Mahfoud F, Ukena C, Lenski M, Yilmaz A, Klingel K, Kandolf R, Sechtem U, Cooper LT, Böhm M. Update on myocarditis. *J Am Coll Cardiol*. 2012 Feb 28;59(9):779-92. doi: 10.1016/j.jacc.2011.09.074. PMID: 22361396.

⁶GORE I, SAPHIR O. Myocarditis; a classification of 1402 cases. *Am Heart J*. 1947 Dec;34(6):827-30. doi: 10.1016/0002-8703(47)90147-6. PMID: 20271990.

⁷Basso C, Calabrese F, Corrado D, Thiene G. Postmortem diagnosis in sudden cardiac death victims: macroscopic, microscopic and molecular findings. *Cardiovasc Res*. 2001 May;50(2):290-300. doi: 10.1016/s0008-6363(01)00261-9. PMID: 11334833; PMCID: PMC7202452.

⁸Towbin JA, Lowe AM, Colan SD, Sleeper LA, Orav EJ, Clunie S, Messere J, Cox GF, Lurie PR, Hsu D, Canter C, Wilkinson JD, Lipshultz SE. Incidence, causes, and outcomes of dilated cardiomyopathy in children. *JAMA*. 2006 Oct 18;296(15):1867-76. doi: 10.1001/jama.296.15.1867. PMID: 17047217.

⁹Mason JW, O'Connell JB, Herskowitz A, Rose NR, McManus BM, Billingham ME, Moon TE. A clinical trial of immunosuppressive therapy for myocarditis. The Myocarditis Treatment Trial Investigators. *N Engl J Med*. 1995 Aug 3;333(5):269-75. doi: 10.1056/NEJM199508033330501. PMID: 7596370.

¹⁰Felker GM, Hu W, Hare JM, Hruban RH, Baughman KL, Kasper EK. The spectrum of dilated cardiomyopathy. The Johns Hopkins experience with 1,278 patients. *Medicine (Baltimore)*. 1999 Jul;78(4):270-83. doi: 10.1097/00005792-199907000-00005. PMID: 10424207.

¹¹Towbin JA, Lowe AM, Colan SD, Sleeper LA, Orav EJ, Clunie S, Messere J, Cox GF, Lurie PR, Hsu D, Canter C, Wilkinson JD, Lipshultz SE. Incidence, causes, and outcomes of dilated cardiomyopathy in children. *JAMA*. 2006 Oct 18;296(15):1867-76. doi:

these difficulties completely insurmountable? Difficulties or not, just as always, we can wait for better times and do nothing or try to cope with what we have and make the best of it. Thus far, armed with the weapons of classical logic, we prefer to face these difficulties in this publication.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Material

Vaccination with messenger ribonucleic acid (mRNA) based anti severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus-2 (anti-SARS-CoV-2)-vaccines were able to save many Covid 19 positive persons from a deadly outcome of their Covid 19 infection. Nonetheless, information about potential long-term health outcomes are still not yet available. Contrary to all expectations, various adverse events (AEFI)^{12, 13} attributed to mRNA based anti-SARS-CoV-2-vaccines have been reported, including deadly myocarditis. Nowever, are there any potentially lethal complication following mRNA-based anti-SARS-CoV-2 vaccination at all?

2.1.1. Study of Schwab et al.

Constantin Schwab et al.¹⁴ investigated the cardiac autopsy findings in 25 persons who have died unexpectedly within 20 days following a mRNA-based anti-SARS-CoV-2-vaccine (Comirnaty[®], BNT162b2 (Pfizer–BioNTech) and Spikevax[®], mRNA-1273 (Moderna)). In the study of Schwab et al., all autopsies (n = 35) were performed at the very renowned Heidelberg University Hospital. Among these 35 cases, 10 patients were excluded from further analysis because autopsies revealed other causes of death. However, even these 10 deceased people were vaccinated with either Comirnaty[®] or Spikevax[®]. Lastly, of the remaining 25 bodies found unexpectedly dead at home within 20 days following SARS-CoV-2 vaccination, cardiac autopsy findings consistent with (epi-)myocarditis were found in five cases. Table 1 is providing an overview of these data.

Unfortunately, various questions must already be asked at this point in the direction of this study. Why did the authors fail to present an appropriate placebo group? As an example, the authors could have examined the contra-lateral jab site of the deltoidal muscle i.e. by various histological examinations, which was not exposed directly to a mRNA vaccine. In case 2, Schwab et al. found a prominent CD4-positive lymphocytic infiltration at the jab site of the deltoidal muscle. In this regard, what was found in the other deceased persons? Why was the investigation for potential infectious agents causing a myocarditis conducted in a more or less very restricted manner? As a potential consequence,

[10.1001/jama.296.15.1867](https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.296.15.1867). PMID: 17047217.

¹²Prevention CfDca. Advisory Committee on Immunization Practices (ACIP). Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) vaccines.

¹³Verma AK, Lavine KJ, Lin CY. Myocarditis after Covid-19 mRNA Vaccination. *N Engl J Med*. 2021 Sep 30;385(14):1332-1334. doi: 10.1056/NEJMc2109975. Epub 2021 Aug 18. PMID: 34407340; PMCID: PMC8385564.

¹⁴Schwab C, Domke LM, Hartmann L, Stenzinger A, Longerich T, Schirmacher P. Autopsy-based histopathological characterization of myocarditis after anti-SARS-CoV-2-vaccination. *Clin Res Cardiol*. 2022 Nov 27;1–10. doi: 10.1007/s00392-022-02129-5. Epub ahead of print. PMID: 36436002; PMCID: PMC9702955.

Table 1. mRNA vaccines and myocarditis death
(Study Schwab et al., 2022)

		Myocarditis death B_t		
		YES	NO	
mRNA Vaccine	YES	5	30	35
A_t	NO	$c=?$	$d=?$	$\underline{A}=?$
		$B=?$	$\underline{B}=?$	$N=?$

only case 5 revealed low viral copy numbers of human herpes virus 6 (HHV6). Nonetheless, based on these very problematic and quite biased data, Schwab et al. tried to establish something like a lethal vaccination-associated myocarditis (LVAM). We must be allowed to ask the question, is such a conclusion factually justified?

2.2. Methods

Avoiding and treatment of logical fallacies addresses one of the most important aspects of any scientific inquiry. Sometimes logically sound definitions are of great help in order to enable us to properly infer **from something known to something unknown**. It also goes without any need of further saying that a definition as such should be logically consistent and correct. However, theoretically, circumstances might exist under which it is required to *deal with erroneous definitions*¹⁵ too.

¹⁵Strobino, Riccardo, "Ibn Sina's Logic", The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy (Fall 2018 Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.), URL = <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2018/entries/ibn-sina-logic/>.

2.3. Def. Myocarditis

2.3.1. Laboratory Evaluation in Myocarditis

The 2013 year statement of the European Society of Cardiology (ESC) on the management of acute myocarditis is recommending the assessment of several serum parameters in order to aid in the diagnosis of myocarditis ¹⁶.

- (O) Erythrocyte sedimentation ¹⁷ rate.
- (O) C-reactive ¹⁸ protein.
- (O) Elevated serum cardiac troponin ¹⁹ , ²⁰ , ²¹ , ²² (cTn).
- (O) Elevated Natriuretic peptides (Nt pro BNP).

2.3.2. Electrocardiographic Evaluation in Myocarditis

Electrocardiographic (ECG) signs myocarditis ²³ are:

- (O) Low QRS voltage ²⁴ (Reason: myocardial edema).
- (O) ST segment abnormalities.

¹⁶Caforio AL, Pankuweit S, Arbustini E, Basso C, Gimeno-Blanes J, Felix SB, Fu M, Heliö T, Heymans S, Jahns R, Klingel K, Linhart A, Maisch B, McKenna W, Mogensen J, Pinto YM, Ristic A, Schultheiss HP, Seggewiss H, Tavazzi L, Thiene G, Yilmaz A, Charron P, Elliott PM; European Society of Cardiology Working Group on Myocardial and Pericardial Diseases. Current state of knowledge on aetiology, diagnosis, management, and therapy of myocarditis: a position statement of the European Society of Cardiology Working Group on Myocardial and Pericardial Diseases. *Eur Heart J*. 2013 Sep;34(33):2636-48, 2648a-2648d. doi: 10.1093/eurheartj/eh210. Epub 2013 Jul 3. PMID: 23824828.

¹⁷Aquaro GD, Perfetti M, Camastra G, Monti L, Dellegrottaglie S, Moro C, Pepe A, Todiere G, Lanzillo C, Scatteia A, Di Roma M, Pontone G, Perazzolo Marra M, Barison A, Di Bella G; Cardiac Magnetic Resonance Working Group of the Italian Society of Cardiology. Cardiac MR With Late Gadolinium Enhancement in Acute Myocarditis With Preserved Systolic Function: ITAMY Study. *J Am Coll Cardiol*. 2017 Oct 17;70(16):1977-1987. doi: 10.1016/j.jacc.2017.08.044. PMID: 29025554.

¹⁸Aquaro GD, Perfetti M, Camastra G, Monti L, Dellegrottaglie S, Moro C, Pepe A, Todiere G, Lanzillo C, Scatteia A, Di Roma M, Pontone G, Perazzolo Marra M, Barison A, Di Bella G; Cardiac Magnetic Resonance Working Group of the Italian Society of Cardiology. Cardiac MR With Late Gadolinium Enhancement in Acute Myocarditis With Preserved Systolic Function: ITAMY Study. *J Am Coll Cardiol*. 2017 Oct 17;70(16):1977-1987. doi: 10.1016/j.jacc.2017.08.044. PMID: 29025554.

¹⁹Jani SM, Nallamothu BK, Cooper LT, Smith A, Fazel R. Beating, Fast and Slow. *N Engl J Med*. 2017 Jul 6;377(1):72-78. doi: 10.1056/NEJMcps1608688. PMID: 28679100.

²⁰Bachmaier K, Mair J, Offner F, Pummerer C, Neu N. Serum cardiac troponin T and creatine kinase-MB elevations in murine autoimmune myocarditis. *Circulation*. 1995 Oct 1;92(7):1927-32. doi: 10.1161/01.cir.92.7.1927. PMID: 7671377.

²¹Smith SC, Ladenson JH, Mason JW, Jaffe AS. Elevations of cardiac troponin I associated with myocarditis. Experimental and clinical correlates. *Circulation*. 1997 Jan 7;95(1):163-8. PMID: 8994432.

²²Aquaro GD, Perfetti M, Camastra G, Monti L, Dellegrottaglie S, Moro C, Pepe A, Todiere G, Lanzillo C, Scatteia A, Di Roma M, Pontone G, Perazzolo Marra M, Barison A, Di Bella G; Cardiac Magnetic Resonance Working Group of the Italian Society of Cardiology. Cardiac MR With Late Gadolinium Enhancement in Acute Myocarditis With Preserved Systolic Function: ITAMY Study. *J Am Coll Cardiol*. 2017 Oct 17;70(16):1977-1987. doi: 10.1016/j.jacc.2017.08.044. PMID: 29025554.

²³Felker GM, Boehmer JP, Hruban RH, Hutchins GM, Kasper EK, Baughman KL, Hare JM. Echocardiographic findings in fulminant and acute myocarditis. *J Am Coll Cardiol*. 2000 Jul;36(1):227-32. doi: 10.1016/s0735-1097(00)00690-2. PMID: 10898439.

²⁴Nakashima H, Honda Y, Katayama T. Serial electrocardiographic findings in acute myocarditis. *Intern Med*. 1994 Nov;33(11):659-66. doi: 10.2169/internalmedicine.33.659. PMID: 7849377.

- (O) ST-T wave changes.
- (O) atrial and/or ventricular arrhythmia.
- (O) sinus tachycardia, ventricular tachycardia, ventricular fibrillation.

2.3.3. Echocardiographical Evaluation in Myocarditis

Early use of the rapid and portable echocardiography is essential to assess the left ventricular (LV) function of patients with acute or non-acute myocarditis. Even a fulminant²⁵ myocarditis is distinguishable from acute myocarditis by echocardiography.

Indicators of acute myocarditis:

- (O) LV systolic dysfunction
- (O) Normal septal thickness at presentation.
- (O) Increased diastolic dimensions.
- (O) Functional regurgitation through the AV valves (as sign of ventricular dilation).
- (O) Pericardial effusion .

2.3.4. Cardiac Magnetic Resonance Imaging Evaluation in Myocarditis

Gadolinium contrast-enhanced cardiac magnetic resonance (CMR) is able to provide unique insights into tissue-level pathologies consistent with myocarditis (Lake Louise criteria²⁶).

- (O) edema (as quantified by global or regional T2 enhancement).
- (O) scar or active inflammation.
- (O) evidence of myocardial hyperemia (by enhancement early after gadolinium).

Contrast-enhanced cardiac computed tomography (CT), 65 technetium-99m-MIBI or thallium-201 single-photon emission CT imaging, 65 indium-111 anti-myosin antibody imaging, 66–69 and 18-fluorodeoxyglucose positron emission tomography et cetera have been used to detect myocarditis.

²⁵Felker GM, Boehmer JP, Hruban RH, Hutchins GM, Kasper EK, Baughman KL, Hare JM. Echocardiographic findings in fulminant and acute myocarditis. *J Am Coll Cardiol.* 2000 Jul;36(1):227-32. doi: 10.1016/s0735-1097(00)00690-2. PMID: 10898439.

²⁶Ferreira VM, Schulz-Menger J, Holmvang G, Kramer CM, Carbone I, Sechtem U, Kindermann I, Gutberlet M, Cooper LT, Liu P, Friedrich MG. Cardiovascular Magnetic Resonance in Nonischemic Myocardial Inflammation: Expert Recommendations. *J Am Coll Cardiol.* 2018 Dec 18;72(24):3158-3176. doi: 10.1016/j.jacc.2018.09.072. PMID: 30545455.

2.3.5. Histological Evaluation in Myocarditis

Histologically, myocarditis is defined according to the specifications of the Dallas criteria due to Caforio et al. ²⁷ , ²⁸ as:

- (1) Inflammatory infiltrate with ≥ 14 leucocytes/mm².
- (2) Up to 4 monocytes/mm².
- (3) Presence of CD3 positive T-lymphocytes ≥ 7 cells /mm².
- (O) Myocyte degeneration and necrosis of non-ischaemic origin .

2.3.6. Statistical methods

The data have been analysed due to optical criteria.

²⁷Aretz HT, Billingham ME, Edwards WD, Factor SM, Fallon JT, Fenoglio JJ Jr, Olsen EG, Schoen FJ. Myocarditis. A histopathologic definition and classification. *Am J Cardiovasc Pathol.* 1987 Jan;1(1):3-14. PMID: 3455232.

²⁸Caforio AL, Pankuweit S, Arbustini E, Basso C, Gimeno-Blanes J, Felix SB, Fu M, Heliö T, Heymans S, Jahns R, Klingel K, Linhart A, Maisch B, McKenna W, Mogensen J, Pinto YM, Ristic A, Schultheiss HP, Seegewiss H, Tavazzi L, Thiene G, Yilmaz A, Charron P, Elliott PM; European Society of Cardiology Working Group on Myocardial and Pericardial Diseases. Current state of knowledge on aetiology, diagnosis, management, and therapy of myocarditis: a position statement of the European Society of Cardiology Working Group on Myocardial and Pericardial Diseases. *Eur Heart J.* 2013 Sep;34(33):2636-48, 2648a-2648d. doi: 10.1093/eurheartj/eh210. Epub 2013 Jul 3. PMID: 23824828.

3. Results

By analysing the same issue based on different data and methodological techniques, the causality of an potential AEFI can be assessed at the population level. However, as a consequence, a systematic assessment of an AEFI at single, individual level, is crucial and appropriate too.

3.1. Population level: without mRNA Covid 19 vaccine no myocarditis: refuted!

Schwab et al. published data on the relationship between mRNA vaccination and myocarditis death (see table 1). Among the 35 cases autopsied at the University of Heidelberg, autopsies of 10 patients revealed other causes of death and were excluded from further analysis. For no apparent reason, the authors did not present a placebo group or control group. For example, the authors could have performed (histological) examinations of the quadriceps femoris muscle, among others, in each deceased patient. Are there any inflammatory infiltrates, monocytes, CD3 positive T-lymphocytes et cetera. Why should a mRNA based anti-SARS-CoV-2-vaccine attack only the human heart muscle? Today, there is no reliable evidence to believe that a mRNA based anti-SARS-CoV-2-vaccine is able to affects only the human heart muscle. However, this was unfortunately left out without a understandable reason. Therefore, in order to examine the relationship between a mRNA based anti-SARS-CoV-2-vaccine and myocarditis death at the population level, we are forced to present a fictitious placebo or control group. We known that non mRNA based children and adults succumb to a biopsy-proven myocarditis death in 9–16% of adult patients with unexplained non-ischaemic dilated cardiomyopathy (DCM) ²⁹ , ³⁰ . As a fictitious placebo group, we present n = 25 **deceased people not vaccinated with a mRNA Covid 19 vaccine**, while 5 of these fictitious placebo group persons died of myocarditis. Table 2 provides us with an overview.

Table 2. mRNA vaccines and myocarditis death
(Study Schwab et al., 2022)

		Myocarditis death B _t		
		YES	NO	
mRNA Vaccine	YES	5	20	25
A _t	NO	5	20	25
		10	40	50

Without the necessity of any further mathematical analysis, the proof provided by table 2 cannot be disputed. The hypothesis (on the population level): without mRNA Covid 19 vaccine, no myocarditis death must be refuted. In the sample investigated as in real life, people died because of myocarditis

²⁹Mason JW, O'Connell JB, Herskowitz A, Rose NR, McManus BM, Billingham ME, Moon TE. A clinical trial of immunosuppressive therapy for myocarditis. The Myocarditis Treatment Trial Investigators. N Engl J Med. 1995 Aug 3;333(5):269-75. doi: 10.1056/NEJM199508033330501. PMID: 7596370.

³⁰Felker GM, Hu W, Hare JM, Hruban RH, Baughman KL, Kasper EK. The spectrum of dilated cardiomyopathy. The Johns Hopkins experience with 1,278 patients. Medicine (Baltimore). 1999 Jul;78(4):270-83. doi: 10.1097/00005792-199907000-00005. PMID: 10424207.

especially if not vaccinated by a mRNA Covid-19 vaccine (n = 5). To get to the point with all clarity. The study by Schwab et al. proves at the population level that **mRNA Covid-19 vaccination is not a necessary condition (Barukčić, 2021, 2022b) of death due to myocarditis**. Such a conclusion is historically more than logical necessary, because fatal myocarditis events occurred especially before the development of mRNA Covid-19 vaccines too. Assumed that the hypothesis (at the population level) without mRNA Covid-19 vaccines no deadly myocarditis were true, this could have not been the case. Thus far, it is proofed for sure that **mRNA Covid-19 vaccination is not a necessary condition for fatal myocarditis**, it makes no sense any more to investigate a possible causal relationship between mRNA Covid-19 vaccination and deadly myocarditis at the population level further. In spite of all rules of human logic, Schwab et al. while deceived by the logical fallacy **post hoc ergo propter hoc** or *death after mRNA vaccination therefore because of mRNA vaccination* reach an unjustified conclusion that “*myocarditis can be a potentially lethal complication following mRNA-based anti-SARS-CoV-2 vaccination.*” However, such a maximally erroneous conclusion at the population level cannot be justified by any evidence.

3.2. Individual level: without mRNA Covid 19 vaccine no myocarditis: refuted!

Well, it is reasonable to assume that supporters of the logically completely unacceptable thesis of Schwab et al. may be inclined to provide counter-arguments such as **no two people are alike, each person is different** et cetera. What may be true at the population level may not be true at the level of an individual human being. Indeed, there are differences between people and the differences between people can not always be simply ignored without any consequences. However, despite all individual differences, people also have many things in common. For example, it does not matter at all whether a person is young or old, whether a person is rich or poor, whether a person is thin or fat, whether a person suffers from cancer or not, without gaseous oxygen every individually different person is not alive. Schwab et al. regrettably ignored that there are circumstances where individual differences between human beings are completely irrelevant. However, Schwab et al. have not been able to provide any evidence on an individual level that a mRNA Covid 19 vaccine is a cause or the cause of fatal myocarditis. The reader has to deal with unnecessary speculations of the authors instead of hard scientific facts. Firstly. Within the sample of n = 35 persons vaccinated by a mRNA vaccine investigated by Schwab et al. 5 persons died because of myocarditis. This is about $\frac{5}{35} \times 100 = 14.3\%$. Other study groups are reporting even higher rates³¹,³²,³³ of deadly myocarditis in persons not vaccinated by a mRNA vaccine. If mRNA Covid-19 vaccination was the cause of fatal myocarditis of the persons investigated, why did only 5/35 mRNA Covid-19 vaccinated people die of myocarditis and not all? This question should have been addressed by the authors, but was not. Regardless of these

³¹Mason JW, O’Connell JB, Herskowitz A, Rose NR, McManus BM, Billingham ME, Moon TE. A clinical trial of immunosuppressive therapy for myocarditis. The Myocarditis Treatment Trial Investigators. N Engl J Med. 1995 Aug 3;333(5):269-75. doi: 10.1056/NEJM199508033330501. PMID: 7596370.

³²Felker GM, Hu W, Hare JM, Hruban RH, Baughman KL, Kasper EK. The spectrum of dilated cardiomyopathy. The Johns Hopkins experience with 1,278 patients. Medicine (Baltimore). 1999 Jul;78(4):270-83. doi: 10.1097/00005792-199907000-00005. PMID: 10424207.

³³Towbin JA, Lowe AM, Colan SD, Sleeper LA, Orav EJ, Clunie S, Messere J, Cox GF, Lurie PR, Hsu D, Canter C, Wilkinson JD, Lipshultz SE. Incidence, causes, and outcomes of dilated cardiomyopathy in children. JAMA. 2006 Oct 18;296(15):1867-76. doi: 10.1001/jama.296.15.1867. PMID: 17047217.

obvious shortcomings of the study by Schwab et al., the proof of causality between a mRNA Covid-19 vaccination and fatal myocarditis has not been successful, especially not on the individual level. In order to prove causality at the individual level, each individual person would have had to act as his or her own placebo or control group, while every single parameter would have to be determined numerous number of times by various different methods. However, far and wide nothing of it. Therefore, it is without any sense to assume that on individual level the study group around Schwab et al. succeeded in proving causality between a mRNA Covid-19 vaccination and fatal myocarditis.

3.3. Population level: if mRNA Covid 19 vaccine then fatal myocarditis: refuted!

We were able to prove beyond any shadow of a doubt that a mRNA Covid 19 vaccine is not a necessary condition of fatal myocarditis. As a result of this, there is no need for further consideration with regard to a possible causal relationship between a mRNA Covid 19 vaccine and fatal myocarditis. However, perhaps a mRNA Covid 19 vaccine is at least a sufficient condition of fatal myocarditis? Let us have a look at the data (table 2) of the study group of Schwab et al. under these perspectives. Table 3 provides us with an appropriate overview.

Table 3. mRNA vaccines and myocarditis death
(Study Schwab et al., 2022)

		Myocarditis death B_t		
		YES	NO	
mRNA Vaccine	YES	5	20	25
A_t	NO	5	20	25
		10	40	50

In case of a sufficient condition relationship between mRNA vaccines and fatal myocarditis, all 25 persons should have died because of myocarditis. In contrast to expectation, only 5/25 persons died because of myocarditis. Therefore, an in-depth statistical analysis of these data is meaningless because 20/25 individuals vaccinated with mRNA did not die of fatal myocarditis. Why has this been the case? Does the RNA Covid-19 vaccination has any protective effects against myocarditis death? The reader may come to his own individual opinion. However, one single person who does not die of myocarditis as part of a Covid-19 vaccination is a sufficient proof that a mRNA Covid-19 vaccination is not a sufficient condition for fatal myocarditis. Meanwhile, millions of people have been vaccinated with a mRNA Covid-19 vaccine without dying from myocarditis. Thus far, after carrying out an inquiry into the issue outlined before, a mRNA Covid-19 vaccination is not a sufficient condition (Barukčić, 2021, 2022a) of a fatal myocarditis.

3.4. *Individual level: if a mRNA Covid 19 vaccine then fatal myocarditis: refuted!*

A far-reaching study of the sufficient condition relationship between a mRNA Covid 19 vaccine and fatal myocarditis on an individual level is meaningless for the reasons detailed above.

4. Discussion

Last but not least, can anything positive be gained from the Schwab et al. study? The study by Schwab et al. reaffirms our confidence into the possibilities and the power of pure, classical logic. We know that it has been historically proven and it is re-emerged again by the Study of Schwab et al. that reducing causality to the logical fallacy **post hoc, ergo propter hoc** is without any epistemological sense. As an example. A proud rooster crows. After that, the sun rises regularly. Is the crowing of the rooster the cause of the sunrise? Stated in other words. A person X was vaccinated with a mRNA Covid-19 vaccine. In about 7 days later person X died. So person X died after the mRNA Covid-19 vaccination and therefore because of the mRNA Covid-19 vaccination. Such a defective or incorrect logic is the basis of the conclusion drawn by the study group Schwab et al. Nonetheless, again and again, we have to accept epistemologically that events which occur one after the other might be causally related, but the same do not have to be. Great precision in this context is required here. A further problem remains, namely that events which occur at the same (period of) time can be causally related, but do not have to be. Causality cannot be reduced to pure coincidence. In this case, causality would be identical with the logical fallacy **cum hoc ergo propter hoc** which is without any sense either. Schwab et al. have merely confirmed that death from myocarditis occurs in the population and deserves more scientific and other attention. Schwab et al. have not even been able to provide even a hint of a proof that mRNA Covid-19 vaccines are a cause or the cause of fatal myocarditis. One can forgive authors for being head over heels in love with every detail of their own work even if obviously missing very important points. However, a fair and objective peer review process should be able to point out possible weaknesses in the article to the authors thus that the same can be considered before publication. Journals should, in principle, be required to provide very detailed information on the names of those who supported or opposed the publication of an article. Lastly, the study by Schwab et al. brings further evidence against any usefulness of today's peer review process. We emphasise this because we cannot escape the impression that today's peer review system is regularly misused to support more or less ideologies and (concrete material) interests than to ensure high quality scientific publications.

5. Conclusion

Based on the data published by Schwab et al. logically we have no other choice but to come to the following conclusion.

There is no causal relationship between mRNA Covid-19 vaccines and fatal myocarditis.

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Erratum

Unfortunately, some misprints appeared in the previous publications, especially in the section of definitions. Some of the misprints have been brought up to date in this publication as far as possible.

Private note

The definition section of a paper need not and does not necessarily contain new scientific aspects. Above all, it also serves to better understand a scientific publication, to follow every step of the arguments of an author and to explain in greater details the fundamentals on which a publication is based. Therefore, there is no objective need to force authors to reinvent a scientific wheel once and again unless such a need appears obviously factually necessary. The effort to write about a certain subject in an original way in multiple publications does not exclude the necessity simply to cut and paste from an earlier work, and has nothing to do with self-plagiarism. However, such an attitude cannot simply be transferred to the sections' introduction, results, discussion and conclusions et cetera.

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I was born October, 1st 1961 in Novo Selo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, former Yugoslavia. I am of Croatian origin. From 1982-1989 C.E., I studied human medicine at the University of Hamburg, Germany. Meanwhile, I am working as a specialist of internal medicine. My basic field of research since my high school days at the Wirtschaftsgymnasium Bruchsal, Baden Württemberg, Germany is the mathematization of the relationship between a cause and an effect valid without any restriction under any circumstances including the conditions of classical logic, probability theory, quantum mechanics, special and general theory of relativity, human medicine et cetera. I endeavour to investigate positions of quantum mechanics, relativity theory, mathematics et cetera, only insofar as these positions put into question or endanger **the general validity of the principle of causality**.

^a<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6988-2780>

^b<https://www.webofscience.com/wos/author/record/1972920>

^c<https://www.scopus.com/authid/detail.uri?authorId=37099674500>

^d<https://www.scopus.com/authid/detail.uri?authorId=54974181600>

^e<https://www.mendeley.com/search/?authorFullName=Ilija%20Baruk%C4%8Di%C4%87&page=1&query=Barukcic&sortBy=relevance>

^f<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Ilija-Barukcic-2>

^g<https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=keywords:%22Baruk%C4%8Di%C4%87%22&sort=mostviewed>

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